

**VALIDITY AND SIGNIFICANCE OF SPORTS GAMES AND HEALTHY
METHODOLOGY IN SPORTS**

Madaminov Mirjalol Polat ugli

Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

Teacher of the "Physical Culture" department of the

Faculty of Exact and Applied Sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11096384>

Annotation: In this thesis, the essence, purpose, tasks of wellness technologies, as well as the relevance and importance of wellness technologies in physical education and sports, and the functions of physical wellness in the formation of a healthy lifestyle today are scientifically substantiated.

Key words: prevention, individualization, optimization, recreation, methodology, physical activity.

Introduction.

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, we can see that there is a gradual improvement in all areas. Physical, political and spiritual changes, renewal in the system of universal human values, all personal needs, requirements and benefits of a person are brought to the first place, especially the spiritual, moral and physical capabilities of the growing young generations are increasing.

A number of decisions and decrees by our head of state aimed at creating a healthy lifestyle in society, strengthening the health of the population, raising a physically healthy, intellectually rich young generation, and ensuring the wide involvement of the population in physical education and sports.

On December 28, 2018, in the address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis, "... it is an urgent task to establish a healthy lifestyle in society, to popularize physical education and sports. To develop sports rapidly, to encourage athletes who have achieved high results in international competitions and we attach great importance to support from now on." In recent years, one of the most important tasks in our Republic is the development of mass sports. The task of educating mentally healthy generations and future patriots of independent Uzbekistan ultimately falls on teachers and specialists.

In accordance with the "National Personnel Training Program" implemented in our country, the development of public sports is an extremely important condition for forming the physical and spiritual health of the growing young generation, striving for a healthy lifestyle and instilling love and affection.

In addition, physical education teachers, sports specialists, and coaches have in-depth knowledge, high qualifications, rich experience and skills, which is the guarantee of training fully mature and morally perfect personnel.

Metabolism in the body adapts to the level of work being performed. One of the strategic tasks of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan is to raise a physically healthy and spiritually mature person who is able to do all good things in the future.

In order to fulfill these tasks, we need to study theoretical knowledge in depth, acquire new knowledge in the formation and improvement of a healthy lifestyle, use educational technologies at the level of modern requirements, and educate the representatives of the future generation as patriots and mature knowledgeable owners of their profession. . In this way, we need to take a new and creative approach to the planning of educational activities and their effective implementation, and approach the work with initiative.

The goal. According to the topic, regarding the relevance and importance of wellness technologies in physical education and sports, wellness technologies are primarily aimed at maintaining and strengthening human health through physical culture. Fitness performance is a mandatory component of any form of exercise. In this regard, all components of physical culture (sports, basic, professional-practical, health and physical culture) perform the functions of health.

Health technology is a medical-pedagogical and social science. undertakes. The main purpose of health care is to create a basis for the strengthening of the family, society, nation and state by controlling and ensuring the health of a particular person.

Health is the greatest wealth of man. Undoubtedly, health is the main condition for the realization of human biological and social functions. This is the basis of a person's self-awareness.

At the same time, in modern society, the need to strengthen health care with the help of physical education, including new and developing equipment and technical means, is increasing. This requires, first of all, specially organized activities designed to effectively solve health problems. One of the main goals of health technologies in physical education and sports is to urge that each person should strive to strengthen their internal capabilities in the body, and that each person should create a "healthy lifestyle" for himself and others, as well as a healthy generation. to live in one's dream and to create an opportunity to achieve it, to encourage health, strengthening and longevity.

A distinctive feature of the use of wellness technologies is an optimal mechanism for optimizing and personalizing people's physical load, taking into account age, gender, labor and educational activities and health.

As a type of health care technology, they have their goals and objectives. The purpose of using health technologies is to improve the population. The goals of using health improvement technologies are:

- Increase the functional capacity of the body;
- Prevention of diseases;
- Optimizing vehicle mode;
- Reduce fatigue due to active rest;
- Individualization of optimal training loads in fitness classes based on the recommendations of sports games;
- The use of exercise in the fight against bad morals;
- Involvement of people of different ages, gender and health status, including disabled people, in active physical education and health classes;
- Introducing healthcare technologies as an integral part of a healthy lifestyle;
- Development of professional activity.

According to the components of health technologies, it can be considered as a type of human activity as a result of human activity and as a set of subject values.

Technologies of wellness as a type of activity describes convenient organizational actions, as well as activities related to the observance of a healthy lifestyle. At the same time, the model of the formation of the effectiveness of the health care is defined as the same type of activity of the health care technologies.

Activities in the application of health technologies are primarily aimed at achieving the greatest impact on health. Health technologies as objective values are material and spiritual values created to ensure the necessary effectiveness of physical and recreational activities. In this regard, the content of health technologies is related to meeting the need for movement and active recreation.

The full implementation of these needs, ultimately, ensures health care, high efficiency and effective life of a person even in working conditions.

The system of practical knowledge from various fields of science in physical education, medicine, psychology and other fields is important in the field of health technologies.

Conclusion.

Forming a healthy lifestyle in our society, creating conditions for the population, especially the young generation, to regularly engage in physical education and mass sports, strengthening the confidence of young people in their will, strength and capabilities through sports competitions, courage and patriotism, developing feelings of loyalty to the Motherland, as well as systematic organization of selection of talented athletes from among young people, and large-scale work aimed at further development of physical education and mass sports is being carried out.

A number of activities are being carried out to involve young people in mass sports in order to organize their free time in a meaningful way, to protect and strengthen their health, and to involve mass sports in the social environment in order to strengthen the health of the population. Giving ideas to the young generation about a healthy lifestyle and the combination of medical culture and sports is one of the most urgent tasks of today.

References:

1. Bobomurodov Norpulat Shirinovich Structures of physical fitness of kurashists // Bulletin of science and education. 2020. No. 4-2.
2. Khudoynazarov, E. (2023). Boshlang'ich ta'limda mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati. Молодые ученые, 1(13), 32-37.
3. Эгамберган, Х. М. (2023). Ўқувчиларда танқидий фикрлашни ривожлантиришнинг педагогик ва методик асослари. Zamonaviy fan, ta'lim va ishlab chiqarish muammolarining innovatsion echimlari, 4, 56-59.
4. Madraximovich, X. E., & Urazboyevna, U. N. (2023). O'quvchilar mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishda sinfdan tashqari ustoz-shogird munosabatlarining ahamiyati. Science and innovation, 2(Special Issue 12), 564-566.
5. Худайназаров, Э., & Куделько, Т. А. (2023). Интерактивные задания на английском языке для студентов с использованием футбольных метафор. Образование в сложном нестабильном мире, 83.
6. Худайназаров, Э. Д., & Куделько, Т. А. (2022). Школа будущего (по материалам опроса школьников России и Туркменистана). In Актуальные проблемы изучения иностранных языков и литератур (pp. 158-163).
7. Davronovich, B. M. (2021). Practical work in primary mathematics education as a methodological basis for the study of mathematics. Asian Journal Of Multidimensional Research, 10(6), 173-176.
8. Madraximovich, K. E. (2020). Improving the methodological training of primary school teachers on the basis of innovative approaches. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 8(7).

9. Худойназаров, Э. М., & Бобожонов, А. Б. Синфдан ташқари ишларда ўқувчиларида мантиқий фикрлашни ривожлантиришнинг иновацион жиҳатлари.
10. Худойназаров, Э. М., Эсонов, Н. А., & Кучкаров, М. У. Преимущества альтернативных методов обучения.

